
143. Gaia's maps of the Milky Way

THE ESA–GAIA ‘Image of the Week’, on the first anniversary of the 34-month Data Release 3 (DR3), 13 June 2023, was a remarkable [multi-dimensional map of the Milky Way](#), produced by the many members of the Data Processing and Analysis Consortium (DPAC, to which all are credited), which I’m reproducing here.

All are projections in Galactic coordinates. Only a brief description of each is given here, with further details given under the ‘more’ link for each description.

STAR MOTIONS (panel 1): Trails showing the displacement of stars on the sky 400 000 years into the future [\[...more\]](#). Acknowledgements: A. Brown, S. Jordan, T. Roegiers, X. Luri, E. Masana, T. Prusti, and A. Moitinho.

STAR AGES (panel 2): The average age of stars in the Galaxy, derived from the CU8 FLAME module (Final Luminosity Age Mass Estimator), based on a random selection of 10 million stars from DR3 (blue are the youngest, red the oldest). Most of the oldest are found outside the Galactic disk [\[...more\]](#). Acknowledgements: O. Creevey, M. Fouesneau, and the Gaia group at MPIA.

STAR BRIGHTNESS (panel 3): This shows the median $G - G_{RVS}$ colour, highlighting the effect of extinction by interstellar dust. G_{RVS} is derived from the integrated radial velocity spectrometer spectra [\[...more\]](#). Acknowledgements: N. Leclerc, P. Sartoretti, and the CU6 team.

VARIABLE STARS (panel 4): The 134 000 RR Lyrae stars for which an estimate of metallicity was obtained from the pulsation period and the Fourier parameters of the G -band light curve. The sources are colour-coded according to metallicity, $[Fe/H]$. The higher metallicity of the RR Lyrae stars in the Milky Way bulge compared to variables in the Galactic halo is evident, as is the lower abundance of RR Lyrae stars in the Small Magellanic Cloud compared to the variables in the Large Magellanic Cloud [\[...more\]](#). Acknowledgements: G. Clementini, A. Garofalo, T. Muraveva, V. Ripepi, R. Molinaro, S. Lecia, and the CU5/CU6/CU7 teams.

EXTINCTION (panel 5): GSPphot provides extinction estimates for individual stars. This map is based on 470 million sources from DR3, with A_0 ranging from 0–4 on the colour scale [\[...more\]](#). Acknowledgements: T.E. Dharmawardena, and the Gaia group at MPIA.

INTERSTELLAR MEDIUM (panel 6): The distribution of diffuse interstellar bands (DIB), colour-coded by the equivalent width of the DIB at 1.8 square degree resolution (HEALPix level 5). Strong DIBs are concentrated towards the Galactic plane [\[...more\]](#). Acknowledgements: H. Zhao, M. Schultheis, and the CU8 team.

RADIAL VELOCITIES (panel 7): The Gaia DR3 radial velocities [\[...more\]](#). Acknowledgements: D. Katz, N. Leclerc, P. Sartoretti, and the CU6 team.

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION (panel 8): Colours indicate stellar metallicity, $[M/H]$, i.e. the mean abundance of all chemical elements except H and He. Redder stars are richer in metals. The data is based on all stars in the Gaia DR3 GSP-Spec database [\[...more\]](#). Acknowledgements: A. Recio-Blanco, and the CU8 team.

SPACE MOTIONS (panel 9): Colours show the line-of-sight velocity of stars (blue approaching, red receding). Lines show the proper motions [\[...more\]](#). Acknowledgements: O.N. Snaith, P. Di Matteo, P. Sartoretti, N. Leclerc, D. Katz, and the CU6 team.

SKY MAP OF BRIGHTNESS AND COLOUR (panel 10): This shows the total brightness and colour of more than 1.8 billion stars released as part of Gaia EDR3 [\[...more\]](#). Acknowledgements: A. Moitinho.

THESE SORTS of figures reveal profound insights into our Galaxy’s structure, dynamics, chemical composition and history. And while those shown here are of our Galaxy’s stellar content only, Gaia is also providing a vast body of information on objects in our solar system and, beyond our Galaxy, on galaxies and quasars.

1. Star motions

6. Interstellar medium

2. Star ages

7. Radial velocities

3. Star brightness

8. Chemical composition

4. Variable stars

9. Space motions

5. Extinction

10. Sky map

